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Social Class And Youth Purchase Of Fashion Clothing In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of social class on youth purchase of fashion clothing in Anambra State. The study was motivated by the increasing importance of fashion clothing as a means of social expression and status identification among youths, as well as the growing influence of socioeconomic differences on consumption behaviour. The study adopted a survey research design and employed a structured questionnaire to collect data from youths across selected urban centres in Anambra State. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The findings revealed that social class has a statistically significant influence on youth purchase of fashion clothing in Anambra State. The regression results showed that social class accounted for a substantial proportion of the variation in youths' fashion clothing purchase behaviour, indicating that socioeconomic status plays a critical role in shaping consumption decisions among youths. Based on these findings, the study recommends that fashion retailers and marketers adopt class-based segmentation strategies and appropriate pricing models to effectively cater to the diverse needs of youth consumers. The study contributes to the existing literature on consumer behaviour by providing empirical evidence on the influence of social class on fashion consumption among youths in a developing economy context.

Key Words: Social Class, Consumer Purchase, Youths, Fashion Clothing

INTRODUCTION

Fashion clothing plays a crucial role in contemporary society, serving not only as a means of protection and modesty but also as a powerful medium for social communication. Through clothing choices, individuals express identity, lifestyle, cultural values, and social status. In modern consumer societies, fashion consumption has become closely linked with social stratification, as people often use clothing to signal their position within the social hierarchy. This makes social class a critical factor in understanding consumer purchase behaviour, particularly in the fashion industry. Social class refers to the division of society into categories based on socioeconomic indicators such as income, education, occupation, and lifestyle. These indicators shape consumers' tastes, preferences, purchasing power, and access to fashion-related information (Etuk, Anyadighibe, Edim & Ukpe, 2022). Individuals from higher social classes often have greater exposure to global fashion trends, higher disposable income, and stronger preferences for branded or luxury clothing (Anyanwu & Chiana, 2022). In contrast, lower social classes may prioritize affordability, durability, and functional value over brand prestige. As a result, social class significantly influences the type, quality, frequency, and motivation behind fashion clothing purchases.

In Anambra State, one of Nigeria's most commercially active and culturally vibrant states, fashion clothing consumption occupies a prominent place in social and economic life. Cities such as Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi are known for bustling markets, fashion retail outlets, and a growing population of style-conscious consumers. The state's dynamic mix of traders, professionals, civil servants, artisans, students, and entrepreneurs creates distinct social classes with varying consumption patterns. Fashion

clothing in Anambra State is often used as a marker of success, respectability, and social mobility, especially during social events such as weddings, festivals, religious gatherings, and business engagements. The increasing influence of globalization, social media, and celebrity culture has further intensified fashion consciousness among consumers in Anambra State. Exposure to international brands, online shopping platforms, and fashion influencers has widened consumer choices while also reinforcing class-based differences in purchasing behaviour. While some consumers pursue high-end designer labels to project affluence and status, others adapt fashion trends to fit their economic realities through locally made or imitation products (Agu & Onuoha, 2016). This highlights the intersection between social class and consumer decision-making in the fashion market.

Social class significantly shapes consumers' purchasing power, brand preferences, and consumption motivations. While individuals in higher social classes tend to favor branded, high-quality, and sometimes luxury fashion clothing, those in lower social classes often prioritize affordability, durability, and functional value (Lawan & Zanna, 2013). However, in Anambra State, these distinctions are becoming increasingly blurred due to factors such as imitation products, credit purchases, social pressure, and the influence of social media. Many consumers now aspire to lifestyles beyond their economic capacity, leading to inconsistent purchasing behaviour and challenges for fashion businesses in accurately segmenting their markets (Gazzola, Pavione, Pezzetti & Grechi, 2020).

Furthermore, most fashion retailers and designers in Anambra State adopt generalized marketing strategies without adequate consideration of class-based consumer differences. This often results in poor product positioning, inventory mismatch, pricing inefficiencies, and low customer satisfaction. The lack of empirical data on how social class influence fashion clothing purchase decisions has limited the ability of stakeholders to develop effective, targeted marketing strategies. Additionally, existing studies on consumer behaviour in Nigeria have largely focused on general consumption patterns, brand loyalty, or pricing strategies, with limited attention given to fashion clothing and its relationship with social class at the state level. This creates a knowledge gap, particularly in the context of Anambra State's unique commercial structure and culturally driven consumption patterns. This study therefore examines the relationship between social class and consumer purchase of fashion clothing in Anambra State. It seeks to analyze how differences in social class in relation to income, education, and occupation influence consumers' purchase of fashion clothing.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Class

Social class refers to a relatively homogenous and enduring divisions in a society, hierarchically ordered and with members who share similar values, interests and behaviour. It is also the division of members of a society into a hierarchy of distinct status classes, so that members of each class have either higher or lower status than members of other classes (Kotler & Armstrong, 2017). Consequently, social class is believed to have certain features such as similarity in behaviour of members in structure, education levels, attitudes and communication styles, income, values, place of living; and possibility of transition from one social class to another (Gherasim, 2013). More succinctly, social class is shaped by an individual's material resources (socio-economic) as well as perceptions of rank vis-à-vis others in society (Kraus, Piff & Mendoza-Denton, 2012)

There are several criteria for categorizing social class. These include: income, living area, education, wealth, family background etc (Allen, 2020). Kraus, Piff and Keltner (2011) specifically classify social class by three variables namely: income, education and occupation. However, Boyce, Brown and Moore (2010) are of the opinion that an individual's judgment of these variables is formed by one's local frame of reference such as, the individuals to whom they compare their material wealth. This implies that more than one person within a similar wealth category might view themselves as belonging to different social classes depending on the individuals to whom they may be comparing their wealth status. Thus, apart from social class being a function of material resources, it is also based on an individual's own construction of social class rank in terms of others within the society (Cohen et.al, 2008).

Mihic and Gordana (2016) argue that some similarities in behaviour could still exist even among individuals or families from different social classes, thereby implying that social class is associated with values and lifestyles of consumers. In their own words, 'personal values and attitudes can have a greater influence to buyers' behaviour than the amount of income they have access to. The implication of this is that members of different social classes that have similar incomes can, depending on their values and preferences spend it on different contents and activities. In relation to values, one can talk about the significant consumers' segment whose income is not high enough to be considered wealthy by the contemporary society. However, in their desire to buy only the best, they buy less often and not as much, but they buy quality goods.'

Categories of social class vary depending on geographical and country characteristics. Kotler and Keller (2012) identified seven social class categories: lower-lowers, upper-lowers, working class, middle class, upper-middles, lower-uppers and upper-uppers. In Nigeria, the Philips Consulting Survey Report (2014) identified three forms of social class mobility, namely: upward, downward and horizontal mobility. While upward mobility refers to an improvement in a person's position overtime that may lead to an increase in status, downward mobility is concerned with a decline in a person's status leading to an undesirable situation where a person's state of living reduces below previously accepted standards. However, horizontal mobility is simply a movement from one position to another still equivalent in social status.

In measuring social class, several subjective, reputational and objective have been suggested. Under subjective measures, individuals are asked to estimate their own social class positions; under reputational measures, informants make judgments concerning the social class membership of others within the community; under objective measures, individuals answer specific socioeconomic questions and then are categorized according to their answers (Kraus et.al, 2012). The modality of this research falls within the last category.

Consumer Purchase of Fashion Clothing

Fashion design focuses on apparel and custom ornamentation depending on culturally and socially accepted standards within a particular period. In contrast to costume design, fashion design creates seasonal products and follows several basic concepts. In simple terms, fashion may be understood as a style that is popular in the present or a set of trends that have been accepted by the larger society (Kaiser, 2019). Fashion is a complex subject that can be linked to society, culture and commerce. It draws from a range of disciplines including psychology, anthropology, art, history, and communication studies. Fashion derives from the Latin *facere* which means to "make" or "to do" (Heller, 2017). While fashion includes clothing, Winter and Young (2014) further note that it goes beyond the function of clothing as protection from weather. Fashion is not merely dress or costume, but is, in fact, a lifestyle that encompasses not only the styles of dressing in the current time but involves human interaction to signify individual and group identity, aspiration, taste and wealth.

Jin and Kang (2019) define it as a "popular or the latest style of clothing, hair, decoration, or behaviour." According to Kaiser (2019), fashion is a form of self-expression with a specific context, such as time, place and purpose. Examples of these are clothing, footwear, lifestyle, accessories, makeup, hairstyle, and body posture. The term implies a look defined by the fashion industry as that which is trending. Everything that is considered fashion is available and popularized by the fashion system (industry and media).

Fashion is defined in several different ways, and its application can be sometimes unclear. Though the term fashion connotes difference, as in "the new fashions of the season", it can also connote sameness, for example about "the fashions of the 1960s", implying a general uniformity. Fashion can signify the latest trends, but may often reference fashions of a previous era, leading to the reappearance of fashions from a different period. Whereas a trend often connotes a peculiar aesthetic expression, often lasting shorter than a season and being identifiable by visual extremes, fashion is a distinctive and industry-supported expression traditionally tied to the fashion season and collections (Kawamura, 2015). Style is an expression that lasts over many seasons and is often connected to cultural movements and social markers, symbols, class, and culture According to sociologist Pierre Bourdieu, fashion connotes "the latest difference (Fletcher, 2020).

Even though the terms fashion, clothing and costume are often used together, fashion differs from both. Clothing describes the material and the technical garment, devoid of any social meaning or connections; costume has come to mean fancy dress or masquerade wear (Gronow, 2018). Fashion, by contrast, describes the social and temporal system that influences and "activates" dress as a social signifier in a certain time and context. Philosopher Giorgio Agamben connects fashion to the qualitative Ancient Greek concept of *kairos*, meaning "the right, critical, or opportune moment", and clothing to the quantitative concept of *Chronos*, the personification of chronological or sequential time (Agamben, 2009).

Clothing (also known as clothes, garments, dress, apparel, or attire) is any item worn on the body. Typically, clothing is made of fabrics or textiles, but over time it has included garments made from animal skin and other thin sheets of materials and natural products found in the environment, put together. The wearing of clothing is mostly restricted to human beings and is a feature of all human societies. The amount and type of clothing worn depend on gender, body type, social factors, and geographic considerations (Toups, 2015). Clothing plays an important role in these developmental processes. Clothing is one of the most expressed symbols of peer identification. Parkins (2015) indicated that youths are in touch with their culture by wearing symbolically valued articles of clothing, such as brand-name athletic shoes or designer jeans. Demanding their products and searching for their own identity, youths from ages 18 to 24 have become an important market segment, especially for clothing products (Evanco & Moutinho, 2016).

Meanwhile, Fashion is also a source of art, allowing people to display their unique tastes and styling (Benton, 2018). Different fashion designers are influenced by outside stimuli and reflect this inspiration in their work. For example, Gucci's 'stained green' jeans may look like a grass stain, but to others, they display purity, freshness, and summer (Kaiser, (2019). Fashion is unique, and self-fulfilling and may be a key part of someone's identity. Similarly to art, the aims of a person's choices in fashion are not necessarily to be liked by everyone, but instead to be an expression of personal taste. A person's personal style functions as a "societal formation always combining two opposite principles. It is a socially acceptable and secure way to distinguish oneself from others and, at the same time, it satisfies the individual's need for social adaptation and imitation (Gronow, 2018). While philosopher Immanuel Kant believed that fashion "has nothing to do with genuine judgements of taste", and was instead "a case of unreflected and 'blind' imitation", sociologist Georg Simmel thought of fashion as something that "helped overcome the distance between an individual and his society" (Gronow, 2018).

Fashion is considered a utilitarian art form, which means that it combines aesthetics with the item's functionality. Choice of fabric and materials does not only entail how good it will look, but how the wearer will feel while wearing the item. The value, quality and characteristics of materials are also considered. For example, creating a silk dress usually requires more subtle styles and decorations, as opposed to creating a winter jacket made of thick wool. Design ideas also depend on the current fashion trend, as dictated by major popular designers such as Dolce and Gabbana or Louis Vuitton and the current trend of popular culture.

Social Class and Youth Purchase of Fashion Clothing

Faced with an ever-increasing selection of clothing brands and products, youths seem to choose their outfits based on conformity and/or differentiation behaviours, notably through groups with distinct linguistic and dress styles (Jeong & Park, 2010). Although marketing research has devoted scant scientific attention to youths and their consumer choices (Derbaix & Leheut, 2018), it would be valuable for researchers and clothing industry professionals alike to better understand the main factors that inform the clothing selection of youths.

In a society where consumption is perceived as a central element in the lives of young adults (Shim, Serido, & Barber, 2011), a wide array of cultural objects (games, sports, music, etc.) as well as articles of clothing define young adults' identity, and allow them to identify with or disassociate from others. The importance of consumption is extremely significant: it is part of their education, contributes to their socialization, and considerably influences their identity and image development (Benn, 2014). Clothing choices are closely linked to the identity of young adults and provide a platform for balancing personal aspirations with desires to conform to peer groups and social trends (Noble, Haytko, & Phillips, 2009).

Youth must be addressed from a marketing standpoint based on internal (personal) and/or social (group) processes. Youths seem to consume products and/or brands specific to their peer group (primacy of social identity), but they may also seek to differentiate themselves from others to assert their individuality (primacy of personal identity) through unique products or brands. Both personal identity (internal process) and social identity (group process) explain the clothing choices of young adults (East, Wright & Vanhuele, 2013), as shown by East et al., (2013) in their work on the impact of self on luxury-brand consumption of young adults, suggests that the impact of identity on youths' clothing choices is both personal and social class, which is in keeping with the relative importance attached to product and/or brand. They showed that social class identity shapes consumers' brand selection.

As a general phenomenon, social stratification tends to be accepted as a fact of life (Benjamin, 2013). Every society stratifies its members into social classes according to their values to the society. The members of a social class share common values and ways of thinking, speaking and behaving (Abraham, 2011). Thus, consumers interact mostly with people of their social class so that each class has the same values and patterns of behaviour. Therefore, marketers must respond specifically to different groups. Marketers increasingly look at social class from a global perspective. In some societies such as India and Brazil class distinctions are clear, and status differences are great. In others such as Denmark and Canada, differences are less extreme. In countries with strong class differences, where people live, the cars they drive, the types of clothing they wear, how much they travel and where they go to college are largely determined by social class (Hollensen, 2010).

Social class has a significant impact on consumer behaviour and this impact may start during childhood. Some researchers argue that Children or young people start learning behaviours and obtaining the habits of lifestyle from their family based on the social class of the family. Hollensen, (2010) argue that in the more affluent families, children acquire some understanding of the purchasing processes at a relatively early age. Previous research findings appear to support this line of reasoning, showing that young people from upper socioeconomic backgrounds have greater awareness of, and preference for, commercial stimuli in their consumer environment. Specifically, some research suggests that young people from upper social classes may have stronger brand preferences and are more likely to seek information before decision-making than their lower-class counterparts (East et al., 2013). Social class influences where and how people feel they should shop. Lower-status people prefer local, face-to-face places where they get friendly service and easy credit, often in the neighbourhood. Upper-middle consumers feel more confident in their shopping ability. They will venture to new places to shop and will range throughout a store to find what they want (East et al., 2013).

In summary, all societies are divided into different groups of people as a fact of real life and these groups of people are defined as social classes. The members of a social class share common values and ways of thinking, speaking and behaving. Social class is determined by income and various other factors such as wealth, education, and occupation. Consumer behaviour is influenced by many individual and environmental factors and we believe that social class is one of the most important one of these factors. For instance, In some countries with strong class differences, where people live, the types of clothing they wear and how they dress are largely determined by social class.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on theory of personality. This theory of personality was proposed by Sigmund Freud in 1923. The theory states that somebody's behaviour is impacted by biological elements by way of drives or instinctive influences that operate outside the conscious thought of an individual. Freud recognized three aspects of the mind known as the superego, the ego and the id which he hypothesized shaped an individual's personality. The ego is associated with the conscious mind and functions under the reality principle and is comprised of feelings, thoughts, lifestyles and memories. He further maintained that the ego was an internal consciousness and drive that executed one's personality.

In relating theory to the study, this would imply that apparel consumers make both conscious and unconscious decisions to purchase from a source. As such, fashion clothing retailers must creatively design emotional and rational advertisements regarding their clothing stores to be able to influence consumers to buy from them. The superego was connected to societal forces and was responsible for the

ethical and moral aspects of a person. This would prompt a person to purchase from fashion clothing retailers who supported social missions. Backing Freud's theory, researchers suggested that retailers ought to provide interesting quality clothing products that help consumers fulfil their moral and social obligations like environmentally friendly fashion clothing products (Nuttavuthisit & Thøgersen, 2017).

In addition to the foregoing, the id comprises all the biological elements of personality that are inherited. The id is impulsive and is responsible for the unconscious behaviour of a person making one respond straightaway to drives. It wants instant gratification for its wishful desires and needs irrespective of the outcome. Freud's theory on the id pleasure principle implies that individual consumers will tend to purchase on impulse based on various drives that prompt them. There are a group of risk-averse consumers who are scared of new brands such as retailers or products (Kovacs & David, 2016). These consumers would, therefore, prefer to buy only products they know or from retailers they regularly purchase from. These consumers are not ready to take chances and are sceptical of new offerings meeting their expectations. Inflexibility is a typical personality trait observed in consumers who only buy fashion brands they are familiar with (He, Zhan & Hu, 2018). Fashion clothing retailers must sample such consumers to enable them to experience new brands and introduce variants under the same brand names to ensure consumers continue to purchase from them. Other consumers are not afraid to take risks and they readily shop for newly designed brands. Fashion clothing retailers should provide new exciting brands and innovations that are popular locally and globally to attract this set of consumers.

Retailers can apply Freud's contribution to create brand appeals towards fantasy and fun (Lowrie, 2018). A pleasant shopping experience will impulsively trigger consumers to purchase from such a retailer. The idea that irrational forces drive unconscious consumer behaviour can be maximized by retailers in their advertising campaigns on products and services (Neese, Foxx, & Eppler, 2018). For example, apparel retailers can entice fun-loving consumers to buy from their stores by using emotional advertising campaigns. Additionally, apparel retailers can apply Freud's contribution by creating a brand image that appeals to consumers' fantasy, deep desire, friendliness or some escape from life. This model provides a useful contribution to the variable of consumer personality and the indicators the study uses to operationalize the variable such as consumer innovativeness, loyalty to favourable retailers and social disposition.

Empirical Review

Etuk et al. (2022) examined the influence of sociological factors and consumer buying behaviour towards fashion clothing. It was carried out to determine the influence of family, peer group, reference group and culture on consumer buying behaviour towards fashion clothing in Calabar. The study adopted cross sectional survey research design. A structured questionnaire was used to obtain primary data from 185 consumers of fashion clothing. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics, while hypotheses testing was done using multiple linear regression. Consequently, the findings of the study revealed that culture had the highest significant positive effect on consumer buying behaviour towards fashion clothing, family, reference group and peer group. The study concluded that sociological factors are key determinants of consumer buying behaviour towards fashion clothing and made practical implications to that effect.

Yiyue (2018) examined the buying behaviours of generation x women on fast fashion products: A mixed methods study. The purpose of this thesis is to investigate and analyze the buying behaviours of the Generation X women on fast fashion products by using mixed methods study. The data generated were analyzed descriptive statistics and regression analysis. Social class, quality and availability of the products were found have the significant impact on consumers' emotion and cognition toward fast fashion buying behaviours. Price was found to have no impact on consumers' cognition towards fast fashion buying behaviour.

Thilini and Aysha (2021) conducted a study on decisive factors that drive consumer perceptions towards branded fashion choices in Sri Lanka. This study was conducted to identify the decisive factor that drives consumer perceptions towards branded fashion choices in Sri Lanka. There were five main factors identified that can affect consumer decision on branded fashion choices in Sri Lank: social class factors, psychological factors, brand related factors, product related factors and marketing tools used by the brand.

The gathered data was processed through SPSS to conduct various tests such as normality, multicollinearity, linearity, descriptive analysis, correlation, regression and so forth. Subsequent to the conducted analyses and tests, it was identified that product related factors have the most impact on consumer perception of branded fashion choices. Although the study was targeted at 300 respondents due to various unavoidable constraints, the information was gathered from 256 respondents. According to the findings a significant portion; 19.5 percent of the respondents would consult their brother and/or sister before the purchase of apparel and respondents who are employed were influenced by their co-workers and would value their suggestions.

Neelam (2018) examined the buying behaviour of youth towards branded fashion apparels in Mawana city. In addition, consumer attributes (i.e., apparel involvement, brand consciousness, reference group, social class, and other factors) and personal characteristics were investigated separately and in relation to the purchase behaviour of youth. Random sampling technique was used to select 200 respondents for the research. Factor analysis was adopted to check the impact of different factors of customers that leads to buying a brand. The finding shows that people get influenced by new fashion but not always. They get influenced in the range of neutral to usually. Most of the people usually get influenced by friends and family. From this factor we conclude that social class, fashion, family and friends influence the choice of brand.

Eze and Bello (2016) assessed the factors influencing consumers buying behaviour within the clothing industry. The study aims at exploring the sociological factors influencing consumers purchasing behaviour in the clothing industry. This study deployed a qualitative approach to exploring key factors influencing consumers purchasing behaviour. More specifically, the study adopted semi-structured interviews with 16 employees of TR Couture. The finding revealed that social class, age, quality, income and fund shapes consumers purchasing behaviour. The implication of this finding is that marketers should constantly study the behavioural patterns of their clients before making plans to buy goods or services sold to consumers as factors explored in this study indicate that they strongly shapes consumers buying pattern.

Khafid et al. (2017) analysed the influence of personal and social identity on the clothing consumption of adolescents in France. The descriptive statistics and the correlation table were compiled using SPSS 21.0. The confirmatory factor analyses and the structural equations required to address the hypotheses were carried out using AMOS 22.0. The results highlight: (i) the influence of identity on the importance attached to product and brand; (ii) the mediating effects of personal and social identities; and (iii) the moderating effects of gender and grade level. The study conclude with an analysis of theoretical contributions, practical implications, and future research directions.

Anyanwu and Chiana (2022) carried out a study on socio-cultural influences on fashion consumption behaviour of university students. The study aimed at investigating the social-cultural influences on fashion consumption behaviour among undergraduate university students basing on the theory of reasoned action (TRA). The population of the study was mainly the Management Science students from two universities from the South-East and South-South Zones of Nigeria. The sample size was 278 while valid response was 256. The survey was based on likert scale structured questionnaire, while the proposed model was tested with the SPSS version 21 Simple Regression Analysis (SRA). It was found that culture, opinion leadership, social class, family and ethnicity have significant influence on fashion consumption among undergraduate students.

Triwijayati, Melany, Wijayanti and Pradipta (2019) investigated the role of social class vs. income in the purchase of consumer products in Jawa Timur, Indonesia. The study utilized a quantitative survey with an *ex-post facto* approach. Respondents were classified by social classes and income levels using the Index of Social Position (ISP); the respondents then filled out a questionnaire on 18 items of purchase grouped into five types, which are food and beverages, clothing, durable goods, investment services, and other products. The research is a survey research. The population of the study consists of 800 respondents in the Province of Jawa Timur. Questionnaire was employed as the instrument of data collection. The relationship of social class and income with product purchase was tested using the Chi Square (χ^2) test. The result showed that social class is linked with the purchase of 17 items, while income level correlates

with all items of products and services that are used. Social class is more linked to milk, fast food, owned and the price of personal and household electronic equipment, and the type of investments and finances. Okonkwo and Moguluwa (2018) investigated the influence of social class on consumers' shopping behaviour in Nigeria. This study was carried out in order to determine whether there is a significant influence of social class on consumers' choice of shopping outlet; and investigate the extent to which social class significantly influenced consumers' organization of purchases, shopping style, and shopping pattern in Nigeria. This study adopted the cross-sectional research approach and the survey research method. Descriptive statistical methods such as frequencies and percentages were used in data presentation. The chi-square and multiple regression statistics were used to analyse data. The results indicate that social class significantly influenced consumers' choice of shopping outlet; social class did not in any way significantly influence consumers' organization of purchases; occupation/profession did not have a significant influence on consumers' behaviour with respect to their shopping style; and income and occupation/profession did not have a significant influence on consumers' behaviour with respect to their shopping pattern.

Mustapha, Mulyana and Yanita (2021) examined the factors controlling consumer's choice on fashion desires and purchase option in Indonesia. Data was collected from a sample of 329 consumers in South Sumatta province in Indonesia. The study employed the multinomial logistic regression analysis to examine the effect of those variables on fashion desires and purchase option. Findings revealed that among the characteristics that influence consumer preferences for fashion desires and purchase option was family and friends reference. The study concluded that social factors are among the key determinants of consumer buying behaviour towards fashion clothing and made practical implications to that effect.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive research design using survey method was adopted for this study. The study was carried out in Anambra State. Anambra is a state in Nigeria. It is located in the South-eastern region of the country. The study was restricted to three major urban cities in the three Senatorial Zones in Anambra State namely; Awka (the State Capital from Anambra Central), Onitsha (commercial hub of the state from Anambra North) and Nnewi (industrial hub of the State from Anambra South). The choice of the three major cities was based on its representation of the various Anambra state economic and social strata and rapid development.

The target population of the study consists of youth consumers of fashion clothing in the three (3) selected cities of Anambra state (Awka, Onitsha and Nnewi). Youths/adults within the ages of 18-45 were considered for the study. Topman's formula was employed to derive a sample size of 379. The respondents for this study were accessed through a judgemental sampling method. The study sample was selected based on availability of youth consumers of fashion clothing in the three (3) selected cities of Anambra state (Awka, Onitsha and Nnewi). The data for this study was obtained through structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics and simple regression analysis was employed in analyzing the data.

RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

Social Class and Youth Purchase of Fashion Clothing in Anambra State

Table 1: I like to buy and wear fashionable and trending clothes that are well known to my friends

	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	38	10.7
Disagree	58	16.3
Agree	156	43.8
Strongly agree	104	29.2
Total	356	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 1 shows that 156(43.8) of the respondents agree that they like to buy and wear fashionable and trending clothes that are well known to their friends. 38(10.7) strongly disagree, 58(16.3%)

disagree, 104(29.2%) of the respondents strongly agree. This implies that the respondents agreed that they buy and wear fashionable and trending clothes that are well known to their friends.

Table 2 I like to wear fine clothes that have high quality

	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	45	12.6
Disagree	44	12.4
Agree	172	48.3
Strongly agree	95	26.7
Total	356	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 2 indicate that 45 (12.6%) strongly agree that they like to wear fine clothes that have high quality, 44(12.4%) disagree, 172(48.3%) agree while 95(26.7%) strongly agree. This indicates that social class influences youth purchase of fashion clothing.

Table 3 No matter the price, I like to buy and wear clothes that make me feel special among my peer groups

	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	56	15.7
Disagree	48	13.5
Agree	158	44.4
Strongly agree	94	26.4
Total	356	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 shows that 46(15.7%) of the respondents strongly disagree that no matter the price, they like to buy and wear clothes that make them feel special among their peer groups, 48(13.5%) disagree, 158(44.4%) agree while 98(26.4%) disagree. This indicates that social class influences youth purchase of fashion clothing.

Table 3: I wear fashionable clothes that are affordable, no matter the quality

	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	53	14.9
Disagree	77	21.6
Agree	135	37.9
Strongly agree	91	25.6
Total	356	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4 indicated that 53(9.0%) of the respondents strongly disagree that they wear fashionable clothes that are affordable, no matter the quality, 77(21.6%) disagree, 135(37.9%) agree while 91(25.6%) strongly disagree. This indicates that social class influences youth purchase of fashion clothing behaviour by creating desire.

Table 5: Quality of clothe is more important than its price to me

	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	56	15.7
Disagree	80	22.5
Agree	131	36.8
Strongly agree	89	25.0
Total	356	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 5 classifies the opinion of the respondents on whether quality of clothe is more important than its price to them. 56(21.6%) strongly disagree, 131(36.8%) agree, 80(22.5%) disagree while 89(25.0%)

strongly agree. This indicates that quality of clothe is more important than its price to some of the respondents.

Estimation Results

Simple regression analysis was employed in analyzing the data and the result is shown in the tables below:

Table 6: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.761 ^a	.579	.575	1.367	.579	162.212	1	118	.000	1.803

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Class

b. Dependent Variable: Youths Purchase of Fashion Clothing

Source: SPSS Version 21

The Table 6 above presents the summary of the regression results. The coefficient of determination (R²) value of 0.579 indicates that approximately 57.9 per cent of the variation in youths’ purchase of fashion clothing in Anambra State is explained by variations in social class. Similarly, the adjusted R² value of 0.575 shows that about 57.5 per cent of the variation in the dependent variable is accounted for by the independent variable after adjusting for degrees of freedom, holding other factors constant. Furthermore, the Durbin–Watson statistic, which is used to test for the presence of autocorrelation in the regression model, recorded a value of 1.803. This value falls within the acceptable range, indicating the absence of autocorrelation among the variables. Consequently, the model is considered stable and the regression estimates are deemed reliable for prediction and inference.

Table 7 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	303.320	2	303.320	162.212	.000 ^b
	Residual	220.647	354	1.870		
	Total	523.967	356			

a. Dependent Variable: Youths Purchase of Fashion Clothing

b. Predictors: (Constant), Social Class

Source: SPSS Version 21

Table 7 presents the result of the F-test, which assesses the overall significance of the regression model. The test produced an F-statistic of 162.212 with a probability (p-value) of 0.000, indicating statistical significance at the 0.05 level. This result demonstrates that the model is well fitted and that social class significantly explains the variations in youths’ purchase of fashion clothing in Anambra State. Consequently, the findings confirm that social class has a significant influence on youths’ purchase of fashion clothing in Anambra State.

Table 8 Regression Result for Hypothesis One

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.305	.734		9.952	.000
	Social Class	.467	.037	.761	12.736	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Youths Purchase of Fashion Clothing

Source: SPSS Version 21

Table 8 reveals that the regression coefficient has a probability (p-value) of 0.000, which falls below the 5 per cent level of significance. This indicates that the result is statistically significant. Consequently, the

null hypothesis is rejected, and it is concluded that social class exerts a significant influence on youths' purchase of fashion clothing in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The sought to determine the extent to which social class influences youth purchase of fashion clothing in Anambra State. The results of the tested hypothesis one revealed that social class has significant positive influence on youth purchase of fashion clothing in Anambra State. This indicates that youths from higher social classes are more likely to spend on fashion clothing than those from lower social classes. This supports previous research suggesting that social stratification shapes consumption patterns, as individuals in higher social classes often have greater disposable income and are more influenced by social norms and trends (Kotler & Keller, 2016). In the context of Anambra State, youths may view fashionable clothing as a symbol of status, prestige, and social identity, motivating them to align their purchases with their perceived social class. This is consistent with Veblen's concept of *conspicuous consumption*, where individuals purchase goods not only for utility but also to signal status and prestige. In practice, this implies that fashion brands targeting youths should consider tiered pricing strategies and aspirational branding to appeal to different social classes. Supporting this assertion, Etuk et al. (2022) ascertained that social class play a role in influencing preference of youth's choice on fashion clothing's. Similarly, Thilini and Aysha (2021) posits that consumers are known to be rational with regard to their purchases, social class factors were found to drives consumer perceptions towards branded fashion choices in Sri Lanka. Khafid et al. (2017) study shares same area of interest with the present study, both used social class in determining consumer's behaviour towards purchase of fashion clothing's. Khafid et al. (2017) study in France revealed that social class has an important attachment to fashion clothing. In addition, Eze and Bello (2016) identified social class as what shapes youths consumers purchasing behavior towards fashion clothing's. The studies concluded that social class factors are key determinants of consumer buying behaviour towards fashion clothing and made practical implications to that effect. This agrees with the findings of Neelam (2018) that social class, family and friends influence buying behaviour of youth towards branded fashion apparels. Similarly, Eze and Bello (2016) found that revealed that social class shapes consumers purchasing behaviour within the clothing industry. Khafid et al. (2017) that social identity influences clothing consumption of adolescents. Anyanwu and Chiana (2022) that social class has significant influence on fashion consumption among undergraduate students. Also, Triwijayati, Melany, Wijayanti and Pradipta (2019) found that social class is link the purchase of consumer products. In the same vein Okonkwo and Moguluwa (2018) found that social class significantly influenced consumers' choice of shopping outlet, shopping style and shopping pattern. Mustapha, Mulyana and Yanita (2021) found that social factors are among the key determinants of consumer buying behaviour towards fashion clothing. Also, Muhammad et al. (2019) social factor positively effects online purchase intention of luxury brand among university students.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the influence of social class on youths purchase of fashion clothing in Anambra State. The discussion highlights that fashion clothing in Anambra State goes beyond basic utility, serving as a medium for social expression, identity formation, and status display. Consequently, consumers' social class significantly influences youths purchase of fashion clothing. Findings from the study indicate that consumers in higher social classes are more inclined toward branded, high-quality, and trendy fashion clothing, driven by greater purchasing power, exposure to global fashion trends, and the desire to maintain social status. Conversely, consumers in lower social classes tend to prioritize affordability, durability, and functionality, although social pressure and media influence often encourage aspirational consumption across class boundaries. This underscores the complexity of fashion consumption in Anambra State, where traditional class distinctions coexist with modern influences such as social media and imitation products. Overall, the study affirms that social class remains a critical determinant of consumer purchase of fashion clothing in Anambra State. By incorporating social class into marketing

and policy decisions, stakeholders can better meet consumer needs, enhance customer satisfaction, and promote sustainable growth within the fashion industry.

The study recommends that fashion retailers and marketers in Anambra State should adopt effective market segmentation strategies that take social class variables such as income, education, and occupation into account. This will enable businesses to design products and marketing messages that align with the needs and purchasing capacities of different consumer groups. Fashion businesses should introduce tiered pricing strategies that cater to different social classes. Offering a range of products from affordable, functional clothing to premium and luxury fashion items will help capture a wider market and reduce the risk of excluding lower-income consumers. The study also recommends that promotional strategies should be customized to reflect class-based consumer behaviour. For instance, social media and influencer marketing may be more effective for younger and higher-educated consumers, while traditional advertising and word-of-mouth strategies may better reach other social groups.

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